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Steering the Artificial Intelligence Landscape: Technological Readiness and Acceptance of Accountancy Students

Bob Agustin M. Gelacio,* Lester T. Amodia, Izza Mae S. Cabaya, Kristine Joy A. Toylo, Juanito C. Dacula Jr.
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

In the vast arena of human advancement, artificial intelligence serves as a transformational force offering boundless possibilities. This study determined the relationship between technology readiness and technology acceptance of artificial intelligence by accountancy students. The study used a descriptive-correlational research design and a complete enumeration technique. The data were gathered from one hundred twenty-five (125) students from the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy program. The technology readiness level of accountancy students in terms of optimism and insecurity is high, while innovativeness and discomfort are moderately high. Moreover, the level of technology acceptance of accountancy students in terms of usefulness and ease of use is also high. The study reveals a significant relationship between technology readiness and technology acceptance of artificial intelligence among accountancy students. With a comprehensive examination of accounting students' readiness and acceptance levels towards artificial intelligence, the study offers essential insights into accounting students' readiness for the seamless integration of artificial intelligence into their academic and professional endeavors.

Keywords: *technology readiness, technology acceptance of artificial intelligence, accountancy students*

Introduction

Technological advent and constant modernization have brought benefits to humanity; the birth of artificial intelligence is a product of innovation intended to ease hard labor. Accounting is an area that has faced threats, challenges, and opportunities due to the technological revolution (Värzaru, 2022). Moreover, modernization in technology has also faced resistance from the people. Factors contributing to this resistance are the deficit in trust, perception of complexity, and uncertainty surrounding the potential benefits (Magnusson, 2022). This necessitates accountancy students' capabilities to adapt and their willingness to utilize artificial intelligence and new technologies (Al-Bari, 2023).

Although the innovation of technologies aims to make people's lives easier, there are still those whose concern is focused on humans becoming obsolete in a society run entirely by robots (Choi, 2021), fear overriding their perception, resulting in a disregard for the advantages of new technologies. In South Africa, accounting students resist technology due to unfamiliarity, perceived difficulty, and anxieties about replacing traditional methods (Terblanche et al., 2022). In Japan, students are hesitant to use technology because they have a negative perception towards it due to a lack of familiarity, fear of change because they prefer traditional methods, lack of confidence, its perceived difficulty of use, and lack of support or training in using it (Sugahara et al., 2022).

A study in Chile showed that the Chilean population is moderately prepared for technological change, with educated individuals being better prepared compared to older adults, suggesting that education is a factor in preparedness for technological changes (Grandon et al., 2019). It is also important to note that the degree of technology readiness of teenagers is affected by parent-child interaction, peers, media, and their perception of themselves (Mishra et al., 2018). Moreover, Damerji (2019) found that technology readiness positively impacts technology acceptance, composed of ease of use and usefulness indicators.

Accountancy students in the Philippines face issues related to technology acceptance (Concepcion et al., 2019). However, it is widely adopted across many sectors; more individuals need help to adopt the technology (Rosales et al., 2020). A study by Amazona and Hernandez (2019) found that students from higher education institutions in the Philippines are reluctant to use technology because of concerns about its reliability and accuracy in predicting academic performance, a preference for traditional methods of learning and assessment, and the belief that it is difficult to use.

The gaps to be addressed in this research are data and geographical gaps. There is a need to resolve the urgent need for more data regarding the relationship between technological readiness and acceptance of artificial intelligence among accountancy students. Moreover, most of these limited studies were conducted abroad, necessitating a study to address this geographical gap. The current research will close both gaps by ascertaining the relationship between technological readiness and acceptance of artificial intelligence among accountancy students in the locality. For the following reasons, the researchers are motivated to study the technology readiness and technology acceptance of artificial intelligence by accountancy students.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aimed to determine the effect of technology readiness on technology acceptance of artificial intelligence of accountancy students. Specifically, it sought to answer the following problems:

1. What is the demographic profile of the students in terms of sex and year level?

2. What is the level of technology readiness in terms of optimism, innovativeness, discomfort, and insecurity?
3. What is the level of technology acceptance of artificial intelligence in terms of usefulness and ease of use?
4. Is there a significant relationship between technology readiness and technology acceptance of artificial intelligence among accountancy students?

Literature Review

Technology Readiness

Technology readiness (TR) refers to the propensity of a population to adopt and use new technologies for achieving goals in both their personal and professional lives (Parasuraman & Colby, 2015). It has four dimensions that collectively explain the technology usage, namely innovativeness, optimism, insecurity, and discomfort (Blut & Wang, 2019). The study of Dissanayaka et al. (2021) showed that TR has a significant positive and moderate level of correlation with the employability of accountancy students.

Meanwhile, the study of Khasanah (2022) disclosed that accountancy students were in the moderate category in TR. It entailed that professional accounting students were neither highly technology-ready nor highly technology-resistant toward utilizing new technologies (Geng et al., 2019). To cope with technological advancement, universities should incorporate artificial intelligence and machine learning in their curricula (Ghosh & Khatun, 2022).

Optimism. According to Napitupulu et al. (2018), optimism can be defined as the degree of confidence that users have in the usefulness of technology for improving productivity in both business and life. In the study of Utami et al. (2022), it was found that students with a higher level of readiness technology optimism are more likely to accept and utilize mobile computing devices for their education because they believe that technology can enhance their overall academic performance by providing accessibility to updated information.

Innovativeness. Innovativeness is defined as the desire always to be a leader in utilizing the latest technology (Napitupulu et al., 2018). Early adopters, teachers who embrace technology before their peers, are well-positioned to recognize the challenges and opportunities of using goods and services tax in geography teaching (Coleman, 2018). This finding was supported by Tenhovirta et al. (2022), who demonstrated that students often seek advice from technology experts among their peers for using new technology through cross-age peer tutoring, emphasizing the importance of collaborative learning and effective technology utilization.

Discomfort. As defined by a study conducted by Blut and Wang (2019), discomfort is the feeling of being overwhelmed by technology and not having control over its use. Putri et al. (2020) highlighted concerns about security, privacy, and unfamiliarity with e-wallets, causing discomfort for users. Similarly, Astuti and Nasution (2014) discovered that entrepreneurs often require user-friendly manuals for high-tech products and services, and limited English language skills hinder their ability to utilize technology and expand internationally.

Insecurity. Bhandari (2022) explained that insecurity is usually a feeling of not being good enough and uncertainty. Cracowski (2023) emphasized that technological tools can harm lifestyles, so people may fear using technology in their everyday lives. Furthermore, Ismail and Wahid (2020) found that motivators (optimism and innovativeness) and inhibitors (discomfort and insecurity) were related to a person's intent to utilize technology, stressing further that the inhibitor shows a significant negative relationship with consumers' intention to purchase online.

Technology Acceptance of Artificial Intelligence

Technology acceptance (TA) is a person's ability and willingness to adopt and use new technologies (Al-Bari, 2023). Different theoretical models of this have been developed, but the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Fred Davis in 1989, is the most widely used (Charness & Boot, 2016). TAM entails that two factors need to be considered to determine whether a computer system will be accepted by its potential users: (1) perceived usefulness and (2) perceived ease of use (Thompson, 2019). Quinto II (2022) emphasized that artificial intelligence can provide opportunities for future accountants to enhance their careers and gain a competitive advantage in the business world. Malaquias et al. (2018) stated that the success of adopting new technologies in universities has a direct relationship with students' acceptance. Resistance to change, organizational culture, lack of trust, and high price of technology are the critical barriers to accepting AI technology in the accounting field (Varzaru, 2022). Etikan and Abasi (2023) also found that TA, which includes perceived usefulness, ease of use, attitude towards artificial intelligence, and trust in artificial intelligence, are the factors that influence the intention to use artificial intelligence to accountancy students in their studies and future professions. Moreover, Accenture (2019) highlighted that AI algorithms are helpful in accounting and auditing jobs because they can process vast amounts of data at lightning speed, eliminating the need for manual input and minimizing human errors.

Usefulness. Lorin (2018) emphasized that the usefulness of applications, particularly artificial intelligence-powered tools, can be determined if workers are more productive and cognitive-oriented. Wang (2023) found that perceived usefulness directly affects the intent of consumers. However, factors such as the individual's attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control can also influence the perceived usefulness of technology (Park & Lee, 2022).

Ease of Use. Alryalat et al. (2016) defined perceived ease of use as the degree to which a person thinks a particular system would be

free of effort. Ibrahim and Shiring (2022) found that perceived ease of use played a significant role in educators' positive overall attitude toward using technology in their teaching. Adding to it is a study by Rachmi and Kartiko (2023), which found that perceived ease of use significantly affects user satisfaction. This is supported by Jin (2014), who states that the perceived ease of use positively affects the perceived usefulness.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a descriptive-correlational research design to examine whether technology readiness impacts technology acceptance of artificial intelligence among accountancy students. As Essel et al. (2022) state, descriptive correlational is a method that defines and distinguishes the relationship of variables from the hypothesis systematically made through statistical testing. According to Creswell (2014), in a correlational research design, researchers use correlation statistical tests to measure the degree of correlation of its variables. This study is descriptive since the data gathered described the age, year level, and level of technology readiness and technology acceptance of artificial intelligence. Further, it is also correlational since it determines the relationship between technology readiness and technology acceptance of artificial intelligence.

Participants

This study was conducted at Notre Dame of Midsayap College, Poblacion 5, Midsayap, Cotabato, to determine accountancy students' technology readiness and acceptance of artificial intelligence. The total enumeration technique is used in choosing respondents for this study, which includes all students enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy program in the first semester of Academic Year 2023-2024, totaling 125 respondents.

Instruments

This study used an adapted questionnaire with minor modifications from Damerji (2019). The questionnaire is composed of three parts. The first part was the demographic profile of the accountancy students, consisting of their sex and appropriate year level. The second part encompassed the technology readiness subdivided into optimism, innovativeness, discomfort, and insecurity. The third part contained information about the acceptance of artificial intelligence by technology, which consists of usefulness and ease of use. The Likert scale was used to determine the answers that best align with the view of the respondents in the second part, where the indicator lies. Usually, it consists of five options, and each question is a statement. The respondent may agree or disagree with the statements according to the following scale: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Moderately Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1).

Procedure

The research process was as follows. The researchers first sought approval from the Dean of the College of Business and Accountancy to conduct the study. They then performed a pilot test among 20 third and fourth-year, randomly selected accountancy students from I-Link College of Science and Technology, Inc. to ensure the adapted questionnaire's reliability. After confirming the adapted questionnaire's reliability, the researchers obtained permission from the Program Head to access a list of all currently enrolled accountancy students for the first semester of the School Year 2023-2024 from the Vice President for Membership of the Junior Philippine Institute of Accountants. With the list secured, the researchers administered the validated questionnaire to the respondents to collect the necessary data. The researchers explained the purpose of the study properly and adequately to the respondents during the administration of the research instruments.

Moreover, they also elaborated thoroughly on the questionnaire to ensure that miscommunication would be avoided and that the respondents understood it entirely. The respondents were given ample time and liberty to ask clarifications upon answering the questions. After retrieving the questionnaires, the researchers tabulated the results and delivered them to the statistician for statistical analysis using appropriate statistical tools and analyses.

Ethical Considerations

The questionnaire used in the study was adapted from Damerji (2019) with minor modifications to suit the needs of this study. The face and content validity of the research instrument was assessed by expert judgments of the teacher, consultant, and instrument validators. Moreover, the Cronbach Alpha of technology readiness based on the original instrument was "0.685", with a score for the indicator of optimism of "0.731", "0.758" for innovativeness, "0.738" for discomfort, and "0.513" for insecurity. Additional scores were "0.949" for usefulness and "0.910" for ease of use, while the overall technology acceptance of AI was "0.93". This means that the instruments used are reliable.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings of the study based primarily on the data gathered. The data are presented in tabular and textual forms.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex and year level. According to the data presented below, 68%

or 85 out of 125 of the respondents are female, while only 40 out of 125 or 32% of the respondents are male. Moreover, on the item that pertains to year level, the result shows that 68 out of 125 respondents, or 54.4% of the total population of the research, are 1st-year students, 32 out of 125, or 25.6% are 2nd-year students, 16 of the total population or 12.8% are 3rd-year students and 9 out of 125 respondents or 7.2% are coming from 4th year.

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of the Respondents*

Item	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	40	32.0
Female	85	68.0
Total	125	100
Year Level		
1 st Year	68	54.4
2 nd Year	32	25.6
3 rd Year	16	12.8
4 th Year	9	7.2
Total	125	100

Level of Technology Readiness

Table 2 summarizes the data gathered on the level of technology readiness in terms of optimism, innovativeness, discomfort, and insecurity. The results revealed that the highest indicator is insecurity, rated as Agree, with an overall mean of 4.05 and a standard deviation of 0.93. On the other hand, discomfort is rated as Moderately Agree with the lowest computed mean of 2.82. The grand mean of 3.51 on the level of technology readiness is also rated as Agree and has an average standard deviation of 0.94.

Table 2. *Level of Technology Readiness*

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Optimism	3.96	0.79	Agree
Innovativeness	3.19	1.02	Moderately Agree
Discomfort	2.82	1.03	Moderately Agree
Insecurity	4.05	0.93	Agree
Grand Mean	3.51		Agree
Average Standard Deviation		0.94	

Level of Technology Acceptance of Artificial Intelligence

Table 3 exhibits the level of technology acceptance of artificial intelligence in terms of usefulness and ease of use. The table shows that the overall level of technology acceptance in terms of usefulness has a calculated mean score of 4.00 and a standard deviation of 0.93, which is described as Agree. On the other hand, the overall mean score and standard deviation of the level of technology acceptance in the aspect of ease of use are 3.52 and 0.94, respectively, and described as Agree. The grand mean of 3.76 on the level of technology acceptance is rated as Agree, and the average standard deviation is 0.94.

Table 3. *Level of Technology Acceptance of Artificial Intelligence*

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Usefulness	4.00	0.93	Agree
Ease of Use	3.52	0.94	Agree
Grand Mean	3.76		Agree
Average Standard Deviation		0.94	

Relationship Between Technology Readiness and Technology Acceptance of Artificial Intelligence

Table 4 presents the relationship between technology readiness and technology acceptance of artificial intelligence of accountancy students using Pearson correlation. The correlation coefficient is significantly different from zero, providing sufficient evidence to conclude that technology readiness and technology acceptance are correlated significantly. The reason for rejecting the null hypothesis is that the p-value of 0.000 is less than the level of significance of 0.05. Moreover, the Pearson correlation coefficient is 0.447, implying a high positive correlation exists between the two variables.

Table 4. *Relationship Between Technology Readiness and Technology Acceptance of Artificial Intelligence*

Variables	N	Df	R-value	p-value	Indication	Decision
Technology Readiness	125	124	0.447**	0.000	Significant	Rejected
Technology Acceptance						

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The results based on frequency and percentage distribution exhibit that the majority of the accountancy student respondents at Notre Dame of Midsayap College are female, which is 68 % or 85 out of 125 respondents. Moreover, most of the respondents are first-year students, with a total of 68 out of 125 or 54.4%.

The level of technology readiness of the accountancy students is based on optimism, innovativeness, discomfort, and insecurity. The accountancy students agreed that new technologies contribute to a better quality of life in terms of optimism. In terms of innovativeness, the results exhibit that the students agreed that other people come to them for advice on using new technology. Moreover, in the aspect of discomfort, the students reported moderate discomfort among students due to the lack of plain language manuals for high-tech products or services. The students indicated in the survey results that too much technology distracts people to a harmful point in terms of insecurity.

In addition, the level of technology acceptance of artificial intelligence by accountancy students is grounded on its usefulness and ease of use. For the usefulness, the accountancy students agreed that using artificial intelligence in future accounting and auditing jobs will enable them to accomplish tasks more quickly. On the other hand, researchers also found that students agree that using artificial intelligence in their future accounting or auditing jobs will increase their productivity. More so, regarding ease of use, the accountancy students agreed they would find artificial intelligence systems in accounting or auditing flexible to interact. However, the students also agreed that they would find artificial intelligence systems to do what they want them to do in accounting or auditing.

Lastly, there is a significant relationship between technology readiness and technology acceptance since accountancy students with high technology readiness and acceptance positively approach artificial intelligence adoption in their studies and profession.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The level of technology readiness and the level of technology acceptance of accountancy students is high. Students generally perceived technology as facilitating progress, task completion, and overall well-being. Furthermore, they expressed concerns about distractions, limitations of virtual platforms, and trust issues. Those with technological expertise were early adopters. While students appreciated user manuals, they found technical assistance communication difficult. High artificial intelligence acceptance was observed among students, who believed artificial intelligence tools could boost productivity. The study emphasizes the connection between technology readiness and artificial intelligence acceptance, providing valuable insights for educators to enhance artificial intelligence-centric curricula and prepare students for AI integration.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Bob Agustin M. Gelacio, CPA, MBA

Notre Dame of Midsayap College – Philippines

Lester T. Amodia

Notre Dame of Midsayap College – Philippines

Izza Mae S. Cabaya

Notre Dame of Midsayap College – Philippines

Kristine Joy A. Toylo

Notre Dame of Midsayap College – Philippines

Juanito C. Dacula Jr., MBA

Notre Dame of Midsayap College – Philippines